

FPGA Implementation of a Linearization System for Wideband Envelope Tracking Power Amplifiers

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Abstract—This paper focuses on the implementation of a linearization system for envelope tracking (ET) power amplifiers (PAs) in field-programmable gate array (FPGA). The ET PA linearization system includes a slew-rate reduction envelope generator, a RF leakage cancellation system in the supply envelope path and a baseband I-Q digital predistorter (DPD). This work targets the implementation of an ET PA linearization system on a radiofrequency system-on-chip (RFSoc) device running under a demanding baseband sampling frequency of 614.4 MHz, which allows handling communication signals with up to 200 MHz bandwidth, considering a DPD bandwidth expansion by 3×. The detail of the FPGA implementation is presented to illustrate the trade-off between hardware resources and linearization performance, i.e., adjacent channel power ratio (ACPR) and error vector magnitude (EVM), under different bit configurations for the arithmetic. The power consumption is also evaluated since it is another relevant performance indicator to be considered in the FPGA implementation of the linearization system.

Index Terms—Digital predistortion, envelope leakage cancellation, envelope tracking power amplifier, field-programmable gate array, high-level synthesis.

I. INTRODUCTION

AMONG the different high efficiency amplification topologies proposed in the literature to cope with the linearity and power efficiency trade-off in power amplifiers (PAs) [1], the envelope tracking (ET) PA architecture has been adopted mainly for user equipment (UE) [2]. In ET PA, the supply voltage is dynamically adjusted according to the instantaneous power demanded by the envelope of the RF signal, as depicted in Fig. 1. A key element in the ET PA system to carry out the dynamic supply modulation is the envelope tracking modulator (ETM). The ETM has to efficiently deliver the instantaneous power required by the transistor at the same speed of the signals' envelope. Since the overall ET PA system's efficiency

results from the product of the RF PA drain efficiency and the power efficiency of the ETM, the design of the ETM is crucial to guarantee high efficiency figures. A typical solution adopted in the literature to cope with the trade-off between bandwidth and power efficiency in the design of the ETM is the linear-assisted hybrid configuration [3]–[5]. In the hybrid configuration, a linear stage inefficiently provides power at high frequencies, while a narrowband switching stage provides the required power at low frequencies with high efficiency [6].

The ETM has a limited bandwidth and thus, when considering the RF amplification of wideband signals, some bandwidth limitation of the supply envelope (i.e., the bandwidth of the envelope is 3× to 5× the I-Q signal bandwidth) prior to the ETM amplification is required. In addition, due to the intrinsic ET topology, the impedance seen at the ETM output changes with time. Due to this load-modulation effect, some unfiltered RF leakage (coming from the non-linearly amplified RF signal) is combined with the supply envelope at the ETM output, significantly degrading the overall linearity at the RF PA output [7].

The ET PA linearization techniques to address the aforementioned source of nonlinear distortion has been addressed by the authors of this paper in [8]. Three main blocks responsible for the trade-off between power efficiency and linearity in the ET PA were proposed. First, a shaping function block is responsible for creating a slower version of the original RF envelope in order to dynamically supply the RF PA. Then, an open-loop (i.e., assuming factory calibration) envelope leakage cancellation (ELC) subsystem is proposed to compensate for the unwanted RF leakage at the output of the ETM. Finally, an I-Q adaptive (closed-loop) digital predistortion linearizer is included as part of the linearization strategy to help meeting the adjacent channel power ratio (ACPR) specifications [9] (i.e., ACPR < -36 dBC) when operating the ET PA with fifth generation new radio (5G NR) wideband signals.

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Fig. 1. Simplified block diagram of an envelope tracking power amplifier.

In terms of hardware implementation, to allow high-throughput digital signal processing (DSP) and fast prototyping, field programmable gate array (FPGA) implementation is without doubt the preferred solution. Several publications can be found in the literature related to the FPGA implementation of digital predistortion linearizers. Just to mention a few recent examples, in [10], the authors proposed a generalized FPGA implementation architecture based on multipliers to compensate the distortion induced by transmitter leakage in concurrent multi-band transceivers with non-contiguous carrier aggregation. Alternatively, in [11], the authors proposed a parallel-processing digital predistortion engine architecture capable to overcome the linearization bandwidth constraint imposed by the maximum clock frequency of the FPGA and thus being able to linearize wideband 5G signals. In [12], the authors presented an efficient implementation of a piece-wise DPD model. From a power consumption perspective, in [13], the authors showed the characterization of the predistorters consumption and linearity performance with clock frequency and bit width. However, to the best knowledge of the authors, for the first time, an integrated FPGA implementation of the subsystems contributing to the linearization of an ET PA operated with 5G NR modulated signals of up to 200 MHz bandwidth is presented in this paper.

Therefore, in this paper, the aforementioned three functional blocks depicted in Fig. 2, are implemented in FPGA to form the complete ET PA digital driver. As discussed in [8], the use of a slow envelope to supply the RF PA (based on a slew-rate reduced version of the original envelope), shows the best trade-off among power efficiency, linearity, bandwidth and implementation complexity. The FPGA implementation of the shaping function block responsible for the generation of slew-rate limited versions of the original envelope was presented by the authors of this paper in [14]. In this work, however, two additional functional blocks to guarantee the ET PA linearity levels (one operating in the supply envelope path and the other at baseband handling complex I-Q signals as shown in Fig. 2), are included and validated through hardware implementations. Therefore, the second functional block implementation consists in the ELC system, which is based on the envelope generalized memory polynomial (EGMP) behavioral model. Finally, the third implemented functional block is a baseband I-Q digital predistorter (DPD), based on the popular generalized memory polynomial (GMP) model.

Unlike other publications where the GMP-based DPD has been implemented in FPGA devices [11], in this paper, specific design details not reported in previously published works, are given taking into account a target throughput (in terms of sampling frequency) of 614.4 MHz. In particular, two different FPGA design and implementation methodologies are compared. The first one is based on the Xilinx Vivado high-level synthesis (HLS) design flow, where the C++ is the entry programming language (i.e., with a given coding style, HLS-specific constructs and syntax) and the second one is a classic hand-written hardware description language (HDL) design flow. Both methodologies are producing synthesized register transfer level (RTL) digital designs, which are finally implemented using the Xilinx Vivado tool. In this paper, we

Fig. 2. Block diagram of ET PA linearization system.

explore the trade-offs of the two design methodologies, which we believe is an important contribution for a broad part of the research community focusing on FPGA implementation of signal processing algorithms. In this respect, we highlight the advantages and pitfalls and finally present a detailed analysis of the timing closure and a comparison of the actual resources usage of both FPGA design approaches. It is important to underline that as far FPGA resource usage is concerned, it was adopted a straight RTL design approach that does not make use of any parallelization technique (e.g., polyphase processing [15]); the latter typically allow to implement high signal bandwidth DSP solutions at the cost of using additional FPGA resources, thus at the cost of top-up dynamic power consumption. The FPGA prototyping stage presented in this paper could be considered as a first important step towards integrating this novel work (the three combined DSP blocks) in a future application specific integrated circuit (ASIC) or system-on-chip (SoC) aiming to serve 5G or beyond 5G (B5G) handsets. A more sustainable use of the battery lifetime and a more energy efficient operation of future B5G handsets is the ultimate goal and impact of the work presented in this paper.

Therefore, this paper is organized as follows. Section II introduces the main blocks forming the ET PA linearization system; including the formulation of the SR reduction shaping function, the EGMP model for leakage cancellation and the GMP model from the conventional I-Q DPD. In section III, in-depth descriptions of the hardware architecture used for the three functional blocks are given. In addition, a comparison of the resource usage, timing and power consumption between the HDL implementation produced with HLS and the hand-written HDL implementation is presented and discussed. In section IV, the hardware-in-the-loop (HITL) experimental setup is described and experimental results are provided, considering the ZYNQ UltraScale+ RFSoc FPGA platform and the ET PA SoC for mobile terminal applications. Finally, section V draws the conclusion.

II. ET PA OPERATION AND LINEARIZATION

The ET PA operation and linearization system is shown in Fig. 2. The shaping function generates the original SR-reduced supply envelope, the leakage cancellation model generates the optimized envelope signal and improves the ET PA linearity, and the I-Q DPD model further enhances the linearity of the ET PA. In addition to the three major blocks, there is also a functional block calculating the absolute value of the baseband signal which is required by these three blocks and is detached from every individual block to optimize resource

usage. Besides, there are already many mature solutions for computing the absolute value such as the CORDIC solution that was adopted for the proposed implementation. The following subsections show the detail of each block.

A. Slew-rate Reduction Envelope Generation

Many shaping functions can be used to generate the supply envelope for the ET PA. In our previous work in [8], we found that the slew-rate reduced (SR) envelope can best trade-off the efficiency and linearity for the ET PA and it was therefore selected in our implementation. Based on the detrouching envelope,

$$Env_{DT}[n] = \left((E_{TH})^p + |u_{BB}[n]|^p \right)^{1/p} \quad (1)$$

where $u_{BB}[n]$ is the complex baseband signal and E_{TH} is a threshold or lower bound of the envelope, and p is the order of the detrouching function. When the baseband input signal magnitude is normalized, the E_{TH} can be understood as an offset percentage. The SR shaping function adds slew-rate limitation on it by the following process,

$$Env_{SR}[n] = \max_{i=0,1,\dots,N_{step}} \left(Env_{DT}[n+i] - i \cdot \Delta V, \quad (2) \right. \\ \left. Env_{SR}[n-1] - \Delta V \right)$$

where $\Delta V = V_{max}/N_{step}$ is the normalized slew-rate constraint, V_{max} is the maximum value of the supply envelope, and N_{step} is the number of steps, a parameter which determines the slew-rate limitation. The SR envelope is then passed to the ELC block to create an optimized envelope for the purpose of leakage compensation.

As discussed in [8], [16], by controlling the shape of the supply voltage and amount of slew-rate reduction (i.e., tuning parameters N_{step} , E_{TH} and p in (1)-(2)), it is possible to trade-off the overall RF PA linearity and power efficiency. Therefore, for example, the higher N_{step} (i.e., the higher the slew-rate reduction) the better the linearity, but at the price of degrading power efficiency and using more hardware resources for the implementation. In section IV, after an empirical search, the SR parameters to conduct the measurements are set to $N_{step} = 60$, $E_{TH} = 0.5$ and $p = 1$, in order to meet the linearity specifications of ACPR < -36 dBc, while trying to maximize power efficiency when operating the PA with a two-channel 5G NR 100 MHz test signal occupying a total bandwidth of 200 MHz.

B. Envelope Leakage Cancellation with EGMP model

The ELC can cancel or mitigate the leakage presented at the output of the ETM [7]. This is achieved by injecting the inverted version of the leakage estimation. The leakage is estimated with the EGMP considering the distorted RF output as the source of such leakage. The EGMP model is a function of the baseband input as follows,

$$Env_{leak}[n] = \sum_{m=0}^{M-1} \sum_{l=0}^{L-1} \sum_{p=0}^{P-1} a_{m,l,p} |u_{BB}[n - \tau_m]| \\ |u_{BB}[n - \tau_m - \tau_l]|^p \quad (3)$$

where τ_m and τ_l (with $\tau_{m,l} \in \mathbb{Z}$) are the most significant sparse delays of the envelope ($|u_{BB}[n]|$) that contribute to characterize memory effects.

The optimized envelope is then simply calculated with a subtraction as

$$Env_{opt}[n] = Env_{gen}[n] - Env_{leak}[n]. \quad (4)$$

From the implementation point of view, the absolute value is already available from the former process when generating the SR envelope. The hardware design needs to implement (3) and (4) with a pipeline architecture. The leakage signal Env_{leak} is an additive term with zero mean, therefore, it is possible to apply feature selection techniques such as orthogonal matching pursuit (OMP) [17] to find out the memory delay and power order combinations that can best estimate the leakage signal. By doing so, we can obtain a set of basis functions, each of which may be represented by a delay pair and the power order. For storing the basis functions, we define \mathbb{M} as the kernel map for ELC, as

$$\mathbb{M} = (\mathbf{m}, \mathbf{l}, \mathbf{p}) = \begin{pmatrix} m_1 & l_1 & p_1 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \\ m_O & l_O & p_O \end{pmatrix} \quad (5)$$

where m_i in row i (with $i = 1, \dots, O$) stores the delay of the absolute value for the first part in (3), l_i and p_i store the delay and the power order for the second part, respectively. With a determined ELC kernel map of \mathbb{M} , (3) can be simplified as follows

$$Env_{leak}[n] = \sum_{m,l,p \in \mathbf{k}} a_{m,l,p} |u[n-m]| |u[n-l]|^p. \quad (6)$$

The estimation of the EGMP model coefficients, $\alpha_{m,l,p}$ in (6), is carried out iteratively following a direct learning (i.e., closed loop) approach. At every training iteration the least squares (LS) solution is calculated to update the coefficients' value. Further details on the parameters extraction of the EGMP model can be found in [8].

C. I-Q DPD with GMP model

The input-output relationship of a digital predistortion linearizer can be described following a matrix notation as

$$\mathbf{x}_{BB} = \mathbf{u}_{BB} - \mathbf{U}\mathbf{w} \quad (7)$$

where $\mathbf{x}_{BB} = (x_{BB}[0], \dots, x_{BB}[n], \dots, x_{BB}[N-1])^T$ and $\mathbf{u}_{BB} = (u_{BB}[0], \dots, u_{BB}[n], \dots, u_{BB}[N-1])^T$, with $n = 0, \dots, N-1$, are the predistorter output and input vectors, respectively; $\mathbf{U} = (\varphi[0], \dots, \varphi[n], \dots, \varphi[N-1])^T$ is the $N \times O$ data matrix, with N being the number of samples and O being the number of basis functions or the order of the model; and $\varphi^T[n] = (\phi_1[n], \dots, \phi_i[n], \dots, \phi_O[n])$ is the vector containing the basis functions $\phi_i[n]$ (with $i = 1, \dots, O$) at time n .

In order to particularize the basis functions $\phi_i[n]$ in the data matrix \mathbf{U} , we can consider a simplified Volterra series model consisting in a generic representation of the GMP behavioral model in [18], where self-memory, lagging and leading cross-memory terms are included. Considering our behavioral model

and (7), we can describe the distortion signal, i.e., $d[n] = \varphi^T[n] \mathbf{w}[n]$ as

$$\begin{aligned}
 d[n] = & \sum_{l=0}^{L_a-1} u_{\text{BB}}[n-l] g_{l,0}^{(a)}(|u_{\text{BB}}[n-l]|) \\
 & + \sum_{l=0}^{L_b-1} \sum_{m=1}^{M_b} u_{\text{BB}}[n-l] g_{l,m}^{(b)}(|u_{\text{BB}}[n-l-m]|) \quad (8) \\
 & + \sum_{l=0}^{L_c-1} \sum_{m=1}^{M_c} u_{\text{BB}}[n-l] g_{l,m}^{(c)}(|u_{\text{BB}}[n-l+m]|)
 \end{aligned}$$

where $u[n]$ is the baseband input to the DPD function. The memory depth and cross memory products are determined by $L_{a,b,c}$ and $M_{b,c}$, while $g_{l,m}^{(j)}(\cdot)$ (with $j = a, b, c$) are the nonlinear functions that depend on the signal's envelope (i.e., the absolute value). As explained in [19], these nonlinear functions can be described by polynomials or B-splines, for example. Focusing on the polynomial representation, the nonlinear functions are defined as

$$g_{l,m}^{(i)}(r) = \sum_{p=0}^{P_{l,m}} w_{l,m,p} r^{2p} \quad (9)$$

where r is the envelope defined as $r = |u[n-l \pm m]|$, $w_{l,m,p}$ are the coefficients of the polynomial basis functions, $P_{l,m}$ is the degree of the polynomial and where only even power terms are considered.

Each of the basis functions $\phi_i[n]$ or DPD kernels will be weighted by the coefficient $w_i[n]$, where the order of the model O is determined by the value of the hyper-parameters (L , M and P). A kernel map, \mathbb{k} , is a list of non-repeated kernels that represent the DPD behavioral model. For the GMP model, each row i (with $i = 1, \dots, O$) in the kernel map stores the delay of the baseband complex-valued input (l), the delay of the envelope (i.e., absolute value of the input signal) (j) and the power value of the polynomial (p), that is,

$$\mathbb{k} = (l, j, p) = \begin{pmatrix} l_1 & j_1 & p_1 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \\ l_O & j_O & p_O \end{pmatrix} \quad (10)$$

Then, the GMP behavioral model in (8) and (9) can be rewritten as follows

$$d[n] = \sum_{l,j,p \in \mathbb{k}} w_{l,j,p} u[n-l] |u[n-j]|^p \quad (11)$$

The kernel map will be used in the hardware design. In order to determine the most suitable kernels or basis functions, feature selection techniques, for example, the family of the matching pursuit greedy algorithms [17] can be used. The doubly orthogonal matching pursuit (DOMP) algorithm used in [20] for DPD purposes is applied in this paper to obtain a sorted (in order of importance) kernel map. Then, according to the required linearization specifications, we can select the final set of coefficients defining our specific DPD behavioral model.

The estimation of the GMP model coefficients, $w_{l,j,p}$ in (11), is carried out iteratively following a closed loop approach, where at every training iteration the least squares (LS)

Fig. 3. SR envelope architecture optimized for throughput.

solution is calculated to update the coefficients value. Note that the EGMP model was trained and applied before training the GMP model. Again, further details regarding the parameters extraction of the GMP model can be found in [8].

III. IMPLEMENTATION WITH HLS AND CUSTOM CODING

In this section, we propose the architecture for implementing the three functional blocks for ET PA linearization. The Xilinx Vivado High-Level Synthesis (HLS) design toolchain was used -initially version 2018.3 and then 2020.2-, targeting a Xilinx Zynq UltraScale+ RFSoc device (xczu28dr-ffvg1517-2-e). The Vivado HLS allows structured C++ code to be synthesized in hardware description languages like VHDL and Verilog. The tool provides an estimation of resource usage, maximum achieved clock frequency and power consumption. In order to acquire precise implementation results and also performance and power consumption metrics, the HLS-synthesized HDL code is used to create a project in the Xilinx Vivado (System Edition), where it is re-synthesized, placed and routed trying to meet the target timing constraints.

A. Slew-rate Reduction Envelope Generator

In the previous work [14], we proposed an architecture for the SR envelope generation optimized for throughput. In order to approach the maximum speed of the FPGA device and operate at a high sampling frequency, we removed the feedback path from (2) by employing a descending memory chain, and obtained an equivalent operation as,

$$\begin{aligned}
 Env_{\text{SR}}[n] = & \max_{i=0,1,\dots,N_{\text{step}}} \left(Env_{\text{DT}}[n+i] - i \cdot \Delta V, \right. \\
 & \left. Env_{\text{DT}}[n-i] - i \cdot \Delta V \right) \quad (12)
 \end{aligned}$$

Fig. 3 shows the block diagram of the implementation architecture. It comprises a detrouching look-up table (LUT), memory chains, and a maximum pipeline. The maximum pipeline is a cascade structure of maximum selectors. And the maximum selector compares two values and returns the bigger one. It is achieved by doing subtraction and then multiplexing according to the sign bit of the fixed data type. Apart from the general architecture, the custom register transfer level (RTL) design of the required arithmetic operations contributes to the maximum achievable clock speed. In this design, the addition and subtraction (AddSub) operations are intensive; they could be implemented either with general programmable logic (PL)

Fig. 4. Block diagram of the EGMP and GMP implementation architecture for ELC and I-Q DPD.

fabric resources, or with dedicated embedded DSP units (e.g., DSP48E2 [21] in Xilinx FPGAs). DSP slices are embedded FPGA building blocks optimized for arithmetic operations that support pipelining, likewise helping to reach very stringent timing constraints at a low power budget. With the help of DSP slices, we have demonstrated in [14] the implementation of the SR envelope generation based on custom RTL coding, reaching the target sampling frequency of 614.4 MHz.

B. Envelope Leakage Canceler and Digital Predistorter

The EGMP model for ELC of (6) and (4) and the GMP model for DPD of (11) share a similar implementation architecture as shown in Fig. 4. It is composed of five parts: 1) an absolute value calculator; 2) a series of LUTs to assist the fast calculation of the polynomial functions; 3) a series of delay lines for storing both the power terms coming out from the LUTs and the input for the EGMP (absolute-valued) or GMP (complex-valued); 4) delay routing circuits for kernel mapping; and 5) a computation pipeline that consists of minimum computational units for GMP or EGMP. In the following subsections, further details on each part of the architecture as well as RTL design considerations will be given.

1) *Absolute value calculator*: The absolute value of the baseband complex-valued input signal is required by all three functional blocks (envelope generation, ELC and I-Q DPD) for the proposed ET PA linearization scheme. However, only one absolute value calculator is needed because the output can be shared among the three functional blocks. For the EGMP and GMP model, the power terms (obtained by indexing the LUTs) are functions of the absolute value. A high-speed and high-precision absolute value calculator is therefore fundamental for a successful implementation. COordinate Rotation Digital Computer (CORDIC) is a simple and efficient way to calculate trigonometric functions [22], including the absolute value calculation. The CORDIC absolute calculation is achieved by multiple steps of digit-by-digit operations. In each step, there is only a sign comparison, a pseudo-division by bit shifting, an addition or a subtraction. There are already many

mature CORDIC IPs available from the FPGA vendors for the RTL design, therefore, we used the Xilinx official one shipped with the Vivado in the case of the manual RTL design. However, the Vivado HLS does not provide a precompiled and verified CORDIC function. Instead, the CORDIC procedure for calculating the absolute value of complex-numbers can be programmed in C++, and HLS can simulate and synthesize the hardware design. To produce a realistic C-Simulation, we programmed the fixed data type C function for the CORDIC absolute calculation, and used the produced absolute value as the input for the simulation.

2) *LUT-assisted nonlinear function calculation*: Once the absolute value is obtained, the values of the nonlinear functions have to be calculated. There are two ways to obtain these values. The first method consists in a direct implementation, where complexity and hardware resources' requirements depend on the type of nonlinear functions used. In the case of polynomial basis, the value is the p^{th} integer power of the absolute value. A series of pipeline multipliers can be used to implement it directly or, alternatively, using the Horner's rule approach as in [23]. Another method is to pre-calculate each nonlinear function and store them in LUTs as proposed in some DPD implementation architectures [24]–[26]. The result of the nonlinear function is obtained by indexing the corresponding LUT with the absolute value. The advantage of using the LUT method is two-fold. First, the logic of indexing a LUT is fast enough and simple. According to the switching characteristics of the Zynq UltraScale+ RFSoc [27], the maximum frequency of BRAM for its speed grade -2 series is up to 738 MHz, which can satisfy our throughput requirement (614.4 MHz sampling frequency). Second, the LUT method is flexible to convey any kind of nonlinear function, for example, the B-Splines nonlinear functions can also be used. The LUT-based DPD implementation in [19] is an example of using LUTs to store different nonlinear functions.

The number of LUTs required is determined by the number of unique values p_i in the kernel map \mathbb{k} or \mathbb{M} . Regarding the implementation, it is important to properly choose the length of the LUT (since it determines its resolution) and the bit width for representing the value (which determines the precision). These two factors affect the output value of the ELC/DPD and have a strong influence on the linearization performance. As BRAM resources are used in the implementation, different length and bit width configurations can result in different BRAM usage. For example, a BRAM18K can store $1K \times 18$ bits of data [28]. If the length of LUT is more than $1K$ or the data width is more than 18 bits, the implementation requires more than one BRAM18K block. In the following section, the impact of the LUT length, bit width and the resource usage will be discussed.

In the HLS C code, the LUTs are represented by a 2D-array. Every nonlinear function own its column in the array, the length of a column is the LUT length, and the number of column is the number of the nonlinear function. At each function call (i.e., at each clock cycle), all LUTs are read at once in parallel and the array partition directive is used to inform the HLS to split the 2D-array into individual columns.

In the C code, the LUT values are stored in a constant array; HLS automatically creates the LUTs for synthesis and implementation.

3) *Memory delay lines*: The ELC and DPD can compensate for the envelope leakage and PA memory effects by using basis functions that include memory, i.e., delayed versions of the kernels. Therefore, the FPGA needs to store the delayed input and its power terms in memory buffers. Fig. 4 shows the use of delay lines to store the delayed value of the EGMP/GMP input and the power terms at the LUTs output. Useful delays are read and then passed to the minimum computational unit across the delay router. Depending on the configuration in the kernel map \mathbb{k} or \mathbb{M} , the memory depth required by each delay line could be different. For simplicity, in this paper, the memory depths have been set equal to the maximum required M , which is the sum of the maximum leading delay L and maximum lagging delay T plus one, i.e., taking the GMP as an example,

$$L = -\min(l, j, 0) \quad (13)$$

$$T = \max(l, j) \quad (14)$$

$$M = T + L + 1 \quad (15)$$

where l is the vector of delays of the complex-valued input signal and j is the vector of delays of the power terms. Besides, since the leading memory involves future (non-causal) values of the input, the hardware has to pretend that $u[n-L]$ is the “current” input, and thus the output always has a latency of L samples. In Vivado HLS, the delay lines are implemented as shifting memories. At each clock cycle, the delay lines are shifted and the values are read in the meantime, thus it is not suitable to use BRAM due to the memory interface limitation. Instead, distributed memory is used, and a complete partition directive is specified to the delay lines. In this way, the Vivado HLS will generate individual memory elements to form delay lines whose values can be read and passed to the DPD computational units in parallel.

4) *Delay routers*: To obtain the correct ELC or DPD output, the specific power terms at the LUT output and the baseband complex or absolute input (both with a certain delay) have to be correctly routed to the computational unit according to the kernel map. We consider a kernel map determined design, i.e., the delays and order combinations are fixed. Using the Vivado HLS, the delay routing is handled automatically, and the only thing we need to do is to mention the delay (array index in each delay line) correctly in the C codes. The delay routing in the implementation is just some wires that connect the value with delays to the corresponding computational units. For the hand-written HDL design, however, the wire assignment has to be addressed carefully with the help of behavioural simulations and taking into account the delay profiles of the basic programmable logic building blocks; the delay routing is typically implemented with flip flops (FF) to acquire the delayed version of the signals of interest.

5) *Computation pipeline*: The computation pipeline is the key to the high throughput implementation. It consists of a series of EGMP or GMP minimum computational units (MCUs). The MCU takes as inputs a delayed power term, its corresponding coefficient and the delayed input, where the

Fig. 5. ELC minimum computational unit (MCU) for implementing the EGMP model.

Fig. 6. I-Q DPD MCU for the GMP model with enabled pre-adder and/or post-adder (every dashed box indicates the use of a DSP slice).

Fig. 7. Post-implementation resources usage of LUT, Flip-Flop (FF), configurable logic block (CLB); and dynamic power consumption estimation of a EGMP MCU for ELC under different fixed data width configurations.

delayed inputs are provided by the delay routers. It computes the product of these values, which is added with the output from the previous MCU. The number of MCUs corresponds to the length (number of rows) of the kernel map, i.e., the number of coefficients. An EGMP/GMP MCU can be described as follows,

$$x = x' + k u w \quad (16)$$

where x' is the output from the previous MCU, u is the input with a certain delay, k is the basis function value with a certain delay, and w is the corresponding coefficient. However, the actual operations for EGMP and GMP are quite different because of the data types of the operands. Fig. 5 and Fig. 6 show the block diagrams of the MCU for EGMP and GMP, respectively.

Each EGMP MCU performs two real-multiplications and

Fig. 8. Post-implementation resources usage, and dynamic power consumption estimation of a GMP MCU for I-Q DPD under different fixed data width configurations.

an add operation, which is straightforward. To deal with the multiplications, we can make use of the DSP48E2 slices. Apart from the AddSub operations that we used for the SR envelope generation, the Xilinx DSP48E2 also supports other DSP operations, e.g., multiplication with pre-adding and post-adding. Each DSP48E2 slice has a 25×18 two's-complement multiplier, a 48-bit accumulator and a power saving pre-adder and post-adder. As shown in Fig. 5, when considering the use of DSP48E2 slices, only two of them are required for an EGMP MCU; one is used for the multiplication at the first stage, and the other one is used for both the multiplication and the addition, activating the post-adding functionality. Fig. 7 shows the resource usage of LUTs, Flip-Flops (FF) and configurable logic block (CLB) in addition to the two DSP slices, and the corresponding dynamic power consumption estimation (for the target operating frequency of 614.4 MHz), with fixed data width from 11 to 18 bits. These values were extracted from Xilinx Vivado after the implementation stage targeting the Xilinx xczu28dr-ffvg1517-2-e device (Zynq UltraScale+ RFSoc). For each case, a small project containing only one EGMP MCU was generated by both HLS-synthesized and custom hand written Verilog coding. By this way, a basic comparison between the Vivado HLS design flow and hand written RTL code is provided. The Vivado HLS used 2 LUT resources, while the hand written RTL code did not make any use of LUTs. The Vivado HLS, however, features lower CLB and FF usage than the RTL coding. We can also observe the growing power consumption with the number of bits, as expected. The additional resources of the implemented hand written Verilog code are, among other reasons, due to the use of the fully pipelined option in the configuration of the DSP48E2 slices, which allows to reach the highest possible operating clock frequencies, and the absence of LUTs which were replaced by other FPGA resources.

Compared to the EGMP MCU, the GMP MCU is more computational intensive, since it needs to perform a complex-multiplication, a real-complex-multiplication and a complex-addition in one clock cycle. Following the notation in Fig. 6, $u \in \mathbb{C}$ is the baseband I-Q input with a certain delay (where

$u_i = \text{Re}\{u\}$ and $u_q = \text{Im}\{u\}$); $k \in \mathbb{R}$ is the selected nonlinear basis (i.e., power terms at the output of the LUTs) with a certain delay; $w \in \mathbb{C}$ is the corresponding complex coefficient and $x' \in \mathbb{C}$ is the output from the previous GMP MCU. Then, the mathematical operation in a GMP MCU is described as follows,

$$p = u_i(w_i + w_q) \quad (17a)$$

$$c_i = p - w_q(u_i + u_q) \quad (17b)$$

$$c_q = p + w_i(u_q - u_i) \quad (17c)$$

$$x_i = x'_i + kc_i \quad (17d)$$

$$x_q = x'_q + kc_q \quad (17e)$$

In (17a), the product p is generated and used in the following stages (17b) and (17c), and thus only three real-multiplications are required to calculate a complex multiplication. The total number of real-multiplications in a MDCU is five, i.e., the use of multipliers can be estimated by the number of coefficient times five. For the GMP MCU, we can make use of the pre-adding and post-adding functionality provided by the dedicated DSP slices, i.e., each GMP MDCU stage can be implemented with one DSP48E2 slice without using PL resources for the addition or subtraction. For (17a), the DSP48E2 slice is configured for multiplication only, since the complex coefficient w is determined, the sum of real and imaginary part can be pre-calculated and stored, likewise avoiding redundant computations and saving power. For (17b) and (17c), both pre-adding and post-adding are enabled. As for (17d) and (17e), only the post-adding is enabled. In fixed-point arithmetic, adding or subtracting two numbers results in a value that has an extra bit compared to the two operands used. A full precision product result has a bit width equal to the sum of the bit width of the operands. Using full precision operations in a GMP MCU pipeline, in practice needs more DSP48E2 resources than those estimated by the tool. For example, assuming that the nonlinear basis, coefficient and the baseband input data type all have the same data width of 16 bits, their product in (17a) produces p with data width of 33 bits. Similarly, the following stage (17b) produces result of 34 bits, then in the last stage of (17d), the product of k (16 bits) and c_i (34 bits) ends up having 50 bits, which requires cascading two DSP48E2 slices. In most cases, it is not necessary to preserve all the precision and thus, the output results of each stage are truncated and only the most significant bits (MSB) are preserved. Fig. 6 shows the block diagram of the MDCU, where the pipeline registers are omitted and each dash line box represents a DSP48E2 slice. Fig. 8 shows the resources usage in addition to the 5 DSP48E2 slices and the dynamic power consumption estimation. In order to increase the confidence level of the Vivado power estimation tool, we have run a post-synthesis functional simulation to generate a switching activity values file (SAIF). The latter helps the Vivado power estimator tool to acquire a deep insight of the signals transitions, and thus enabled a more accurate dynamic power estimation.

For data width of 18 bits, the Vivado HLS uses more LUT resources but less FF and CLB compared to the manual RTL project. The power consumption also grows with the number

of bits configuration. According to the power estimation of the HLS generated project with 18 bits data width, the power consumption of a GMP MCU (32 mW) is around 3 times of the consumption of a EGMP MCU (11 mW). As in the case of the EGMP, the hand-written Verilog code is using maximum pipelining at all stages to achieve higher clock frequencies, which has an impact on the resource usage. Full pipelining is still not possible in the HLS-synthesized code for the Vivado HLS versions we used, since the code style and directives cannot fully exploit the pipelining options in DSP48E2 slices. As it was already been discussed in [14] and will also be covered in the next section, this majorly affects the timing closure of the digital design.

C. Resource Usage and Timing Analysis

As we already mentioned before, the goal of the FPGA implementation presented in this paper is to serve as a feasibility study and a first step towards an eventual ASIC design, where digital logic resources and mainly power consumption could be further optimized. Thus, given the target application of the system presented here, it is important to understand that the FPGA implementation could serve as a reference to ASIC or SoC designers of 5G and B5G handsets.

When it comes to high-speed RTL designs with bit-intensive arithmetic operations, e.g., multiplications, DSP48E2 slices are definitely the most adequate FPGA building blocks compared to other PL resources like LUTs. Having this in mind, a fixed-point logic data type of 18 bits was carefully selected after conducting simulations in order to find the best trade-off between precision and required performance. Two bits represent the integer part; the first one is reserved for the sign, whereas the second bit is preserved in case overflow occurs during the AddSub operation. The easiness of coding in C++ and synthesizing RTL code in Vivado HLS allowed us to experiment with different synthesis options, coding styles and HLS directives that force the use of specific FPGA resources. For instance, early explorations allowed us to compare designs with and without using DSP48E2 slices. In those preliminary tests, the HLS tool correctly estimated that the RTL design synthesized around LUTs and FFs will not meet timing in an eventual Vivado implementation. In fact, given the very challenging system clock, the HLS estimation was quite pragmatic, taking into account the combinational delay that implies an RTL design built around LUTs and FFs. By applying the “use_dsp” directive in the HLS synthesis, we forced the use of DSP48E2 slices, leveraging higher clock frequencies, since as already highlighted, the architecture of the DSP48E2 slices is optimized for high speed arithmetic operations.

The implementability of the Verilog RTL code synthesized with the Vivado HLS framework, had to be validated in the Vivado Design Suite. As Xilinx indicates, the Vivado HLS tool only produces estimations for the synthesis results, the timing closure and the power consumption. For this reason, we used the Xilinx Vivado System Edition to re-synthesize, place, and route the HLS-produced Verilog RTL design, as well as the hand-written version of the Verilog RTL design. We used Vivado version 2018.3 and 2020.2, in order to maintain

compatibility with third party tools. Initially, the validation of the implementability was made for each one of the three main parts of the system, namely the SR reduction, the EGMP and GMP, in separate Vivado projects. This modular validation allowed us to trace more easily performance bottlenecks.

The maximum frequency a design can run on hardware in a given implementation is:

$$F_{\max} = 1 / (T - \text{WSN}) \quad (18)$$

where WSN is the worst negative slack of the clock signal in the intra-clock paths section (taking positive or negative value) and T is the target clock period, which was set to 1.63 ns (614.4 MHz). In the case of the RTL code produced by the Vivado HLS for the SR reduction, the design had a WNS of -0.632 and did not manage to meet timing. In practice, the maximum clock frequency the design could run on hardware was approximately 443 MHz. Similar implementation timing failure results were produced in the case of the HLS-based RTL code of the EGMP and GMP system building blocks. Hence, despite the precise resource utilization estimated by the Vivado HLS software, the estimation related to the RTL design timing closure proved to be optimistic (i.e., the HLS tool reported that the design would meet timing). In contrast, the highly optimized hand written Verilog code was successfully synthesized and implemented, meeting the timing constraints in all three Vivado projects.

Focusing on the Xilinx Vivado implementation flow, we investigated how the HLS directive that forces the use of DSP48E2 slices is materialized in the synthesized Verilog code. By visualizing the system schematic after the Vivado synthesis, we found out that the DSP48E2 instance has the clock input connected to GND. The same applies to the rest of the options of the DSP48E2 macro, apart from the “OPMODE” input, which defines the type of operation that is carried out. Having such configuration, the internal registers (FFs) of the DSP48E2 slice serving pipelined processing are bypassed. Thus, the DSP48E2 slices are slowed down, a fact that heavily affects timing performance, and ultimately impairs meeting such challenging timing constraints. Despite not satisfying timing closure, the HLS projects that forced the use of DSP48E2 slices still yielded better timing compared to other design approaches making use of LUTs (i.e., due to lower combinational delay) [14]. We also tried to employ hardware-friendly C++ coding styles in Vivado HLS (e.g., breakdown multiple arithmetic operations in separate simple operations), and tried to customize the Vivado HLS DSP directive to enable the DSP48E2 internal pipelining following the related Vivado HLS User’s Guide guidelines, but eventually, we reached to the conclusion that such option is not yet provided in the Vivado versions we have used. While it is not clear the reason that pipelining could not be activated in the HLS DSP directive, we are positive that once this feature will be enabled in future Vivado HLS versions, the synthesized designs would be able to serve ultra high-speed RTL coding requirements.

Table I shows the resource usage and the achieved operation frequency of the two design methodologies, using, as already mentioned before, 18 bits for the fixed point data width. Comparing the results, we observe the impact of different coding

TABLE I
IMPLEMENTATION RESULTS FOR THE TWO METHODOLOGIES

Resource	HLS Implementation			Custom RTL Impl.		
	Used	Available	Util. %	Used	Available	Util. %
CLB LUTs	11254	425280	2.65	6469	425280	1.52
CLB Registers	20318	850560	2.20	92662	850560	10.89
CARRY8	1265	53160	2.38	34	53160	0.64
Block RAM Tile	5	1080	0.46	0	1080	0
RAMB18	10	2160	0.46	0	2160	0
DSP48E2	622	4272	14.56	796	4272	18.63
Achieved Frequency	431.4 MHz			709.7 MHz		

styles on the use of FPGA resources. The implementation based on the Vivado HLS uses more CLB LUTs, CARRY8 and embedded BRAMs compared to the implementation of the hand-written RTL code, while the latter uses more CLB Registers and DSP48E2 resources. To understand the differences, we should mention indicatively that, in the hand-written RTL code, the LUTs are implemented with distribute memory resources instead of embedded BRAM blocks. Moreover, in the hand-written Verilog code speed optimized customizations of the DSP48E2 slice macro have been employed for all real and complex multiplications, which resulted in using more DSP48E2 slices. The hand-written Verilog RTL code allowed a more rich use of Xilinx FPGA processing resources, a fact that was crucial for being able to meet the challenging timing constraints. As the Vivado HLS tool versions mature, features are expected to be added to enable ultra high speed RTL coding.

IV. EXPERIMENTAL SETUP AND HARDWARE-IN-THE-LOOP PERFORMANCE

The integrated FPGA project of the ET PA linearization system is designed containing all the building blocks (CORDIC absolute value calculator, SR envelope generator, GMP predistorter and EGMP leakage canceler) presented in the previous subsection. In order to evaluate the final performance, we have set up an ET PA hardware-in-the-loop (HITL) testbed. As depicted in Fig. 9, the testbed includes an ET PA system-on-chip (SoC) from Hi-silicon, a Xilinx RFSoc FPGA board, an arbitrary waveform generator (AWG), an oscilloscope, pre-amplifiers and power supplies. Despite the fact that the RFSoc 2x2 board has two output ports, the interface between the RFSoc and the RF SMA connectors employs DC blocks and RF transformers suited for direct RF synthesis and acquisition but not to generate the envelope signal which has DC component. Therefore, we use the FPGA for generating the signal samples in numerical format and then send them through the AWG by using the Matlab interface.

The testing signal is a two-channel 5G NR 100 MHz signal (with 273 resource blocks, 30 KHz subcarrier spacing and 64 QAM at every channel), occupying a total bandwidth of 200 MHz. Every data batch consists of 0.5 ms of transmitted signal, which contains 1 slot in a 30 kHz subcarrier spacing (SCS) subframe. Considering a baseband clock of 614.4 MHz (corresponding to an observation and predistortion bandwidth at baseband around 300 MHz), the number of data samples for every batch is 307,200. We configured the SR envelope generation function with $N_{steps} = 60$ for an offset percentage

(a) Block diagram of the testbed

(b) Image of the testbed

Fig. 9. The ET PA linearization HITL test bench. The labels are: (1) ETM+PA: Hisilicon’s ETM and RF PA; (2) USB-MIPI: USB to MIPI adapter; (3) Diff-Amp: differential amplifier THS4508RGT from Texas Instruments; (4) Pre-Amp: RF pre-amplifier ZHL-42 from Minicircuits; (5) DSO: Digital oscilloscope RTP084 from Rohde and Schwarz; (6) AWG: Arbitrary wave generator M8190A from Keysight; (7) RFSoc 2x2: Xilinx Radio Frequency System-on-Chip (RFSoc) board.

of 50%. The EGMP and GMP models consisted of 32 and 64 properly selected coefficients using the DOMP algorithm. After the DOMP selection (see [8] for further details), the maximum nonlinear order was 5 for the EGMP model and 8 for the GMP model; similarly, the maximum delay (memory depth) was 14 samples for the EGMP model and 16 samples for the GMP model. With this configuration, we performed an offline training in Matlab (following an iterative direct learning approach) to obtain the coefficients’ value for both the EGMP and GMP models. We linearized the ET PA improving ACPR performance from -23 dBc to below -36 dBc to set the Matlab baseline reference models used for the FPGA implementation.

Fig. 10 shows the normalized mean squared error (NMSE) performance and the dynamic power consumption of the three main blocks under different data width settings. The Env_{opt} for ELC is generated on top of the Env_{gen} (i.e., the SR envelope), therefore, it shows NMSE degradation when compared to the SR envelope. Our particular GMP model is not working properly (with a NMSE around 14.7 dB) when the data width < 14 bits, due to an overflowing problem caused by the lack of precision. Therefore, at least 14 bits are required for the integrated project. According to the power estimation, considering the operating frequency of 614.4 MHz,

Fig. 10. NMSE between outputs produced by FPGA and Matlab; dynamic power consumption estimation of the integrated ET PA linearization system under different data width configurations.

the data width configuration can cause 1.5 W of difference in terms of dynamic power consumption, which is around 27% of difference with respect to the maximum consumption of around 5.5 W. This tendency is normal, considering that increasing the length of the fixed-point logic data type requires the use of more FPGA resources. The same tendency has also been highlighted in figures Fig. 7 and Fig. 8. As already mentioned before, the confidence level of the Xilinx dynamic power estimation was high due to the use of the SAIF files (i.e., extracted by post-synthesis timing simulation). However, as it can be observed in Fig. 10, there is an inconsistency in the power consumption trend for the case of 18 bits, where we note an unexpected drop. Such inconsistencies are typically observed in incremental RTL implementation of digital circuits, where the synthesizer in the absence of HDL-specific attributes, macros or directives, it may opt for different synthesis strategies due to the inherent randomness of its operation (i.e., a fact that modifies the switching activity and thus the resource usage and eventually the power consumption estimation). Similarly, during the implementation stage, multiple well-defined placement constraints can force the use of the same subset of FPGA resources, helping to control deviations like the ones observed in Fig. 10. However, we did not proceed with such methods since the power consumption trend is well observed in almost the entire curve, and such tight control of the implementation is usually the goal in ASIC design that is out of the scope of this paper.

Fig. 11 shows the AM-AM and AM-PM plot of the ET PA output, using the input data generated by the FPGA with 18 bits of fixed point resolution. We can observe that by only enabling the ELC, the AM-AM has a notable improvement, especially at higher amplitude, but the AM-PM improvement is not evident. With both ELC and I-Q DPD, the AM-AM was further improved and the AM-PM also presents a significant improvement. Fig. 12 shows the spectra of the ET PA output with the comparison between the Matlab baseline and the FPGA with 14 and 18 bits configuration. Using 18 bits can reach almost the same linearization performance as the Matlab baseline, while there is a slight ACPR degradation on the left side out of band when using the 14 bits configuration. For the envelope side, Fig. 13 shows the output envelope spectra; both

Fig. 11. AM-AM and AM-PM plot of the ET PA output with the FPGA produced inputs for ELC only and ELC+DPD.

Fig. 12. ET PA output spectra, using the Matlab produced inputs and the FPGA produced inputs at 14 and 16 bits configuration.

Fig. 13. ETM output envelope spectra when using the Matlab produced ELC inputs and the FPGA produced ELC inputs with different bit settings.

the 14 bits and 18 bits configurations were very close to the Matlab baseline. Fig. 14 shows the concatenated constellation plot of the two 5G NR 100 MHz channels. Finally, Table II

Fig. 14. Constellation of the two NR 100 MHz channels concatenated.

TABLE II
ET PA LINEARIZATION PERFORMANCE

	NMSE (dB)	ACPR (dBc)	Pout (dBm)	Eff. (%)	EVM (%)
w/o Linearization	-16.75	-23.00	24.33	8.35	8.26
ELC Matlab	-21.43	-33.34	24.41	9.11	3.20
ELC FPGA 14 bits	-21.41	-33.30	24.42	9.12	3.32
ELC FPGA 18 bits	-21.44	-33.36	24.40	9.08	3.25
ELC+DPD Matlab	-31.46	-36.44	24.25	8.84	2.02
ELC+DPD FPGA 14 bits	-31.03	-36.12	24.28	8.87	2.10
ELC+DPD FPGA 18 bits	-31.71	-36.42	24.30	8.91	2.03

shows the ET PA linearization performance in terms of NMSE, ACPR, output power, efficiency and EVM with the HITL testbench. For the combined ELC and DPD integrated project, when moving the data width from 18 bits to 14 bits, there is a NMSE loss of around 0.7 dB and a degradation of the ACPR of 0.2 dB. The integrated ET PA linearization system improved the EVM from 8.3% to 2%. Therefore, on the one hand, if we want to keep the best linearization performance, we can adopt the 18 bits FPGA implementation. On the other hand, if the power consumption is prioritized, with the 14 bits configuration is still possible to meet the linearity requirements of ACPR < -36 dBc.

V. CONCLUSION

An FPGA implementation of ET PA RF front-end digital linearization system was presented in this paper. It includes three main functional blocks, i.e., supply envelope generation, envelope leakage cancellation and conventional baseband I-Q DPD. Such system was implemented and deployed on a RFSoc device by loading coefficients that were empirically found with an off-line Matlab training test bench for the EGMP and GMP models. The HITL experimental result showed that the proposed implementation can reproduce the signal input with fair enough numerical resolution. With 18 bits of data width, we could reach a linearity performance as good as the Matlab baseline. We can also reduce the data width to 14 bits for power saving at the price of losing very little linearity performance. We illustrated the entire

implementation process. First, we used the HLS tool for fast prototyping and performance evaluation. Then we moved on to the RTL implementation in Vivado. Having in mind to meet the demanding sampling frequency of 614.4 MHz, we also analyzed the timing closure by comparing the output produced by HLS and a custom RTL design. We intensively optimized the timing based on the manual RTL project, since we can have more control and flexibility on the building blocks. Finally, the integrated ET PA linearization system was carried out featuring a maximum achievable sampling frequency of 709.7 MHz, and being able to handle a 5G-NR signal with a total bandwidth of 200 MHz.

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